

THE GROWTH AND THERMAL STABILITY OF UNIDIRECTIONALLY

SOLIDIFIED Nb-Nb₂C COMPOSITES

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By a floating zone melting and freezing technique, eutectic and hypereutectic Nb-Nb₂C alloys may be grown with well aligned two phase composite structures. The morphology of the carbide phase may be rod-like, plate-like or a combination of rods and plates depending on the growth rate and carbon content. The rod spacing or plate-spacing is a function of growth rate. The structural stability of as grown rod-like Nb-Nb₂C composites grown at two different growth rates and the stability of deformed Nb-Nb₂C composites have been examined after isothermal annealing at temperatures in excess of one-half the eutectic temperature for periods up to 700 hrs. During annealing of the deformed composites the carbide phase undergoes two dimensional coarsening; the rod density is decreased but a high aspect ratio is maintained. After a long anneal the rods combine to form plates. Deformation and high temperature exposure of the composites lead to the breakdown of the fibers along their length and the spheroidization fibers into globules.

Introduction

In recent years unidirectionally solidified metal-matrix composites have gained great attention as possible substitute materials for high temperature and high strength structural applications (1-3).

Binary eutectic alloys can be made to solidify with a micro-morphology that contains a high aspect ratio and anisotropic arrangement of the two phases. Generally the micromorphology consists either of alternating lamellae of the phases or rods of one phase in a matrix of the second. However, to obtain such aligned structures one is not restricted to binary eutectic systems alone. Aligned structures have been obtained in ternary and other complex systems as well (4-6). The volume fraction of the reinforcing phase may be varied by growing the composite at off eutectic compositions (7-9). Well aligned microstructures have been obtained by normal freezing, zone melting and freezing and by Czochralski techniques. For the fabrication of composites of reactive and refractory metals and their compounds, containerless melting, namely floating zone melting and freezing, has been found to be advantageous (9). The primary consideration in controlled eutectic solidification is maintaining a steady planar solidification front.

The performance of aligned duplex structures in service would depend on the stability to high temperature exposure and stresses of the microstructure that develops during solidification. Since the two phases of the eutectic reaction are in chemical equilibrium and the interface between phases is generally a low energy interface, the aligned duplex structure is expected to be stable up to the eutectic temperature. However, the volume fraction of the second phase may change if there is a difference in solid solubility between the eutectic temperature and room temperature. A great deal of work has been done on the thermal stability of lamellar (10-12) and rod eutectic composites (13-18). Various models have been developed to explain the coarsening behavior observed in lamellar and rod-type eutectic composites (11,17-18).

The refractory metal-refractory metal carbide systems such as Nb-Nb₂C, Ta-Ta₂C, etc. offer potential for high temperature and high strength applications. The work reported herein is on the growth of composites in the niobium-niobium carbide (Nb₂C) system by an electron beam floating zone melting and freezing technique and on the thermal stability of the aligned duplex structures that develop during solidification.

Experimental Procedure

Rods of eutectic composition were prepared by carburizing

niobium rods at the eutectic temperature (9,19). The composites were grown using an electron beam floating zone melting and freezing apparatus, by electron beam welding four feed rods together and starting a liquid pool at the bottom of the sample and traversing from bottom to top. Two passes were made before the final growth pass to homogenize and refine the microstructure. The liquid zone length was kept at about 6 m.m. The growth rates used ranged from 5 to 87 microns per second (i.e., 87 to 31 cm/hr). The samples were mounted, polished, etched (a solution of 30 cc nitric acid, 70 cc lactic acid and five to six drops of hydrofluoric acid) and characterized using an optical microscope.

Cylindrical samples of 1/4" diameter x 1/4" for isothermal annealing experiments were obtained from two rods of eutectic composition directionally solidified at 24 microns per second and 87 microns per second. The samples were annealed at 1125°C and 1500°C for various lengths of time in a high temperature vacuum furnace. Isothermal annealing experiments were conducted on specimens with rod-like and lamellar carbide morphology. The progress of coarsening was followed quantitatively by withdrawing samples at various intervals and determining the rod density along the transverse section of the sample as a function of time. To determine the stability of the structure after deformation to high temperature exposure another sample was given 20% cold work by rolling the sample with the rolling direction parallel to the growth axis. The sample was examined before annealing and at various intervals of time during annealing at 1500°C.

Eutectic Microstructure

Well aligned two phase microstructures of niobium carbide in a matrix of niobium have been grown from the melt at the eutectic and hypereutectic compositions. Figure 1 compares the photomicrographs typical of longitudinal sections of as carburized rods, that is before an electron beam zone melting pass, and of specimens directionally solidified by electron beam zone melting and freezing. Aligned duplex structures have been obtained in this system for hypereutectic compositions as well, thus varying the volume fraction of the carbide from 0.26 (eutectic composition) to about 0.33 (at hypereutectic compositions) (9). Efforts to increase the volume fraction of the carbide phase beyond about 0.36 resulted in stray dendrites that nucleated ahead of the freezing interface. The temperature gradient in the liquid ahead of the solid-liquid interface reached by the zone melting configuration was not high enough to suppress these stray dendrites. The dendrites grew ahead of the general interface and were incorporated at random in the aligned duplex structure.

Transverse morphology of the carbide phase varied from lamellar to lamellar plus rod-like to purely rod-like. The typical

transverse photomicrographs in Figure 2 show the lamellar and rod-like carbide morphologies observed in this system. Two factors have been found to influence the variation in carbide-morphology, namely growth rate and composition, Figure 3. The growth rate affects the morphology of the carbide phase in that for a given composition the carbide is plate-like at the lower growth rates, mixed at intermediate growth rates and rod-like at the higher growth rates studied. This is a feature that has been observed in other systems (20-21). The composition (carbon content) affects the morphology in that for the higher carbon contents, the plate-like morphology is stable to higher growth rates. Such a change in morphology with composition and thus the volume fraction of the second phase may be attributed to the minimization of Nb/Nb₂C interfacial area created per unit volume and hence the free energy associated with the interface (22-23).

The lamellar spacing has been found to depend inversely on growth rate and to be substantially independent of composition. For this system a lamellar growth relation of the type $\lambda = AR^n$ with a slope $n = -0.4$ and the intercept $A = 3.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{n+1}/\text{sec}^n$ was derived from the results. (λ is the lamellar spacing and R is the growth rate.) For rod-like carbide morphology the number of rods increased and the inter-rod spacing decreased with an increase in growth rate.

Thermal Stability

Nb-Nb₂C aligned duplex structures showed good microstructural stability. The major change on exposure of these samples to temperatures between one-half and two-thirds of the eutectic temperature for periods up to 700 hours was a reduction in the total number of carbide fibers with no "fiber shortening" or agglomeration along the longitudinal direction, Figure 4. Figure 5 shows the variation in rod density with time for rods grown at different growth rates and annealing temperatures. The samples grown at higher growth rates showed a sharp reduction in the number of rods per cm² within the first 100 hours and then a more gradual reduction. The samples grown at a lower growth rate showed a gradual reduction in the number of rods per cross section. However, the reduction in the rod density at 1125°C was considerably slower than at 1500°C.

This reduction in rod density on annealing is due partly to a two dimensional coarsening phenomenon similar to "Ostwald ripening" (24-26) and due partly to alignment of rods to bring about a transition from the rod-like to the plate-like carbide morphology. In the former case the driving force for the microstructural change is the reduction in the Nb/Nb₂C interfacial area per unit volume and hence the reduction in the free energy associated with the interface.

Examination of the longitudinal section of the annealed samples revealed no change. In the Nb-Nb₂C system, the volume fraction of the second phase is large enough to avoid pinching and agglomeration along the longitudinal direction as exhibited by some low volume fraction second phase composite structures (16,27). This behavior of pinching and agglomeration has been described in detail for cylindrical fibers in terms of volume fraction by Cline (17). Also, the transverse cross sections of the carbide rods are not circular; the rods retain crystallographic facets (Figure 6a) that are associated with specific crystallographic interfaces (28). Hence, the constraint placed on these low index and low energy interfaces may avoid any degradation in the structure (13).

In addition to the two dimensional coarsening of the rods, during the long time exposure of the samples to high temperature, coarsening proceeds through a series of steps shown in Figure 6. There is a transition in carbide morphology from rod-like to plate-like. The transition here seems to occur mostly by rods aligning and joining along the minor axis of the rod cross section to form a plate. In any one grain the major axes of the rods are directed along the same direction. However, such a transition calls for a diffusion controlled rod migration and alignment phenomenon rather than fault migration and annihilation observed in other systems (17-18). In a process such as this strain energy and anisotropy in surface energies may play an important role. The role of strain energy in aligning precipitate particles has been shown for various systems by Ardell and Nicholson (29).

Composite samples having lamellar carbide morphology were annealed at 1500°C for periods up to 100 hours. The carbide plates were observed to coarsen; however, the lamellar morphology was retained.

Metallographic examination of the cold rolled sample showed numerous cracks in the carbide fibers, Figure 7a. On annealing, the carbide phase spheroidizes destroying its continuity in the matrix. A typical sequence of the spheroidization process is shown in Figure 7. In addition to the introduction of cracks, the deformation processes have been found to destroy the presence of low energy interface between the phases (12,14,30). Hence, in the deformed Nb-Nb₂C composite, aided by the "high diffusivity paths" due to the presence of cracks and destruction of the presence of low energy interface, the carbide fibers tend to reduce their interfacial area through the process of agglomeration. Such a breakdown in microstructure could be deleterious in service. Cracks may be introduced into the composite structure during grinding and machining operations as well as by deformation processing.

Summary and Conclusion

Eutectic and hypereutectic Nb-Nb₂C composites have been grown successfully by a floating zone melting and freezing technique. The morphology of the carbide phase changes as the growth rate and/or composition change.

The aligned duplex structure has been found to be fairly stable to high temperature exposure. There is a decrease in rod density in the plane transverse to the growth direction with no agglomeration along the growth direction. The absence of agglomeration has been attributed to the low index low energy interface between the niobium and carbide phases observed in this system. In addition to the two dimensional coarsening manifested as a reduction in the rod density, one of the most interesting phenomena observed during isothermal annealing experiments is the transition in the carbide morphology from rod-like to plate-like. The latter appears to result from migration of the rods through the matrix until they impinge and coalesce.

Thermal stability of deformed composite structures has been found to be poor, leading to the breakdown of the alignment and spheroidization of the carbide phase.

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1. Typical photomicrographs of longitudinal sections of Nb-Nb₂C samples, (a) as carburized and (b) directionally solidified by zone melting. (200X)

a

b

2. Photomicrographs of the transverse sections of Nb-Nb₂C composites showing (a) plate-like carbide morphology and (b) rod-like carbide morphology. (100X)

3. Structures of directionally solidified Nb-Nb₂C rods as a function of growth rate and atomic percent carbon. Volume percent of Nb₂C is shown on the top axis.

4. Photomicrograph of the longitudinal section of a sample annealed at 1500°C for 500 hours showing no degradation in the structure. (200X)

5. Effect of heat treatment on the carbide fiber density in Nb-Nb₂C composite structures.

6. Photomicrographs of transverse sections of Nb-Nb₂C composites showing the effect on carbide morphology of isothermal annealing at 1500°C for (a) 0 hrs., (b) 300 hrs., and (c) 500 hrs. (500X)

7. Photomicrographs of longitudinal sections of Nb-Nb₂C composites showing the effect of deformation and annealing at 1500°C for (a) 0 hrs., (b) 100 hrs., and (c) 500 hrs.